

Experimental Article

HARD PASS

An Arts-Based Autoethnography Regarding the Experience of a Graduate Student of Mathematics

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ABSTRACT: This arts-based autoethnography explores the experience of a graduate student of mathematics at a mid-sized research university through a collection of collage, songwriting, and personal essays. This research identifies issues in the mathematics academic pipeline associated with gender, burnout culture, perfectionism, mental health, qualifying exams, and isolation. The present research is synthesized with existing research on doctoral attrition. Possible positive futures of graduate education in mathematics are discussed.

KEYWORDS: *autoethnography; mathematics; graduate education; attrition; arts-based; critique*

Article begins on the next page.

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Do all work on a separate paper. Turn in this page and all pages with work on them. This is a closed book exam.

Part I - Definitions

Com

HARD

topological spaces

(4) (5 points) Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a surjective function where X and Y are topological spaces. The function f is a *quotient map* if ...

Part II - Do

1. (25 points) Show that $B_\epsilon(x)$

$x \in X$ and $\epsilon > 0$.

2. (25 points) function and K if and only if

$f : X \rightarrow Y$ a f is continuous

3. (25 points) (a) Show that there exists a c is the identity

quotient map if $f \circ g : Y \rightarrow Y$

(b) Apply part $X, (x, y) \mapsto x$

$p : X \times X \rightarrow$

About This Project

Autoethnography is a social research method that, in contrast with what the “hard sciences” consider good research, is quite “soft.” However, as a mathematics education researcher who has read about a lot of social science research methods, I am excited to pull this particular form of research into the field of mathematics. A brief explanation: autoethnography is “research, writing, story, and method that connect the autobiographical and personal to the cultural, social, and political” (Ellis, 2004, p. xix). Another way to think about it is applying social science theories to yourself, or researching yourself. As you can probably imagine, there is a significant amount of variance in this research method. Autoethnography can take a number of forms, including poetry, fiction, novels, photographic essays, and more (Ellis, 2004, p. 38). The idea is that the self and the society are inextricably linked, and much knowledge can be generated from self-reflection. Autoethnography leans into the truth that the researcher cannot be separated from the research; that is to say, there is no way research can be truly objective.

Usually, autoethnography is written. As a musician and visual artist, I thought I would reach more compelling ideas by incorporating arts-based research (ABR) methodology. ABR “involves adapting the tenets of the creative arts in a social research project. Researchers aim to address social research questions in holistic and engaged ways in which theory and practice are intertwined” (Leavy, 2017, p. 9). ABR can involve any art form, including music, visual arts, writing, and dance. Art is thought to access knowledge that is otherwise hidden, tapping into different ways of knowing and expression. What a research participant might not be able to disclose in a spoken interview might be able to express that knowledge through art. Combining ABR with autoethnography is not a novel concept (Ellis, 2004, p. 215), but it’s not very common.

I have opted to use collaging as the primary artistic component of my arts-based autoethnography. This choice happened by happy accident: my partner and I started collaging on a whim, and I noticed myself expressing some important thoughts and feelings about my mathematics graduate program through the art. For me, collaging is a special artistic form because it feels low stakes. In other forms of visual art, I feel a pressure to make something perfect, but when I play with scraps from old magazines and junk mail, I find it easy to relax into the process. This fulfills one of the traits of good autoethnographic writing according to Ellis – writing as a therapeutic practice (Ellis, 2004, p. 135). I have become somewhat of a collaging evangelist, encouraging everyone I know to get some paper scraps together and try collaging as a soothing, possibly introspective, reflective pastime. I have had experiences making collages that are complete nonsense or just visual fun. On the flipside, I have created collages about a feeling or experience that has helped me better understand myself once I took a step back from the collage and saw what I had inadvertently created! Collaging can be an interesting and healing outlet to understand experience.

This paper is originally my master’s thesis in a graduate program of mathematics and has been adapted for this journal. I was enrolled in a PhD program in mathematics with a concentration on math education. In the following pages you will see a collection of my collages meditating on the experience of being a graduate student of mathematics. I have included my interpretations of the meaning of the pieces, but my hope is that you will look at the art and make your own interpretation in addition to mine. Among the collages, you will find a collection of short essays regarding my experience as a mathematics graduate student, including a review of previous research on the topic. As this is a multimedia project, I have also opted to include two songs that I wrote about my experience in the mathematics program. I wrote these songs with no intention to include them in academic work, but I realized that they are rich with meaning and reveal some important perspectives on my experience. A QR code on those pages will take you to the audio

recordings of these songs. You are invited to skim the writing and just take in the art, pick and choose from my essays, or read out of order. I also invite you to get out your scissors and glue stick and collage with this paper (if you printed it out).

Before I continue, I also want to address the incomplete nature of this work. While I believe that social scientists have good intentions in incorporating diverse practices into the field, such as autoethnography and ABR, I abhor the need to legitimize knowledge through academic research. Self-reflection and the arts have always been legitimate forms of knowledge, social scientists are just relabeling these practices in order for them to be accepted by the academic community. I suppose the fault lies in academia. Proponents of ABR and autoethnography are trying to access and include important perspectives, but in order for those perspectives to be taken seriously by academics, they need to be called “research.” Our concept of good research is based entirely on a white, western, male academic tradition, and it is unfortunate that we need to legitimize art and self-reflection through this preexisting tradition by coming up with fancy names for intuitive practices. One way I am hoping to push back on academic tradition is by opting for a more conversational style of prose; one of the most consistent sins in academia is its dense writing style, limiting its audience only to those who have the time and educational background to untangle the unapproachable language.

I chose autoethnographic methodology for this project because it is the most authentic way for me to express my experience in this program. I have been told that the only way to complete a master’s project/thesis/dissertation without dehumanizing yourself is by choosing to work on something you absolutely love, or at least something you can fully and honestly immerse yourself in for many, many hours. For me, I am already engaging in self-reflection on the experience of mathematics graduate school, and I would be making art about the experience regardless. Rather than forcing myself to churn out an academic research paper on a topic I am not feeling connected to, it makes a lot more sense to lean into what I am inclined to work on anyway, both in subject matter and choice of methods. I also think that autoethnographic and arts-based work has the potential to resonate with readers in a way that traditional academic writing cannot access: the paper that comes to mind is “A Dialogue Among Bilingual Language Educators: An Exploration of Female Attrition in the Doctoral Pipeline” by Colomer, Olivero, and Bell (2015). I read this trio-autoethnography in one of my classes and noticed that both myself and many of my peers in the class really connected with this work. For many students, the paper (which is basically a story about some educators wanting to drop out of their doctoral program) hit very close to home, was incredibly validating of their own experiences, and had an emotional impact that more traditional papers didn’t reach. I find this very inspiring and motivating, and I hope that this work will connect with some other graduate students who read this.

On the next pages you will see two collages. On the page following the collages, you will see my written explanations of the collages. I encourage you to fully consider the art and make your own interpretation of the work before reading my explanation.

Article continues on the next page.

White, male, neurotypical, and wealthy

I had to write a diversity statement for one of my seminars this year and print it out for peer feedback. I don't think the diversity statement I wrote was very good, but I cut out this sentence from it because I thought it might be fun to incorporate into a collage. The man on the ladder is positioned above and out of reach of the woman in the bottom left corner. The text "ANXIOUS 67%" shows the way that anxiety disproportionately affects women. The thought bubble above the man reflects men's confidence, and the book near the woman's hand shows women's need to always cite their sources, while men can just say things from their brain and be believed.

CALM

This one is about men! I feel like I am surrounded by super-confident men. It feels impossible to look away from them; in a way, their presence is distracting in an unnerving way. I feel that when you look at the running man, the cartoon businessman doing a backflip, the falling businessman silhouette, you feel overwhelmed and off-balance. The eye in the center is meant to reflect how I am feeling constantly scrutinized and compared to my male counterparts. The blue silhouette with the number 2 shows the anonymity of the men I'm speaking of- I do not feel scrutinized by specific men, but by men in a vague general way. I worry about the way I'm dressing, the way I speak, what men might think about my unshaved body hair and buzzcut. The woodworker in the background represents the indifference I sense from men, feeling like their work is much more important and demanding than mine, so they can't even be bothered to look up. The sideways graph in the upper left corner shows a basic misunderstanding of mathematical conventions I feel that I have. I represent myself in the shadow of the man holding the megaphone: screaming to be heard but ultimately lost in the shadows of men.

The Impact of Capitalism and Girlbossery on (My) Education

I have been reading a lot of research literature about improving mathematics education over the past year, and almost every introductory section cites a similar motivation: mathematics education should be improved so students can compete in the job market, so people can get higher paying jobs, so the United States can “compete internationally,” so historically marginalized students will stay in the field and improve diversity in mathematics, among other improvements (Freeman et al., 2014; President’s Council of Advisors on Science and Technology, 2012; Saxe & Braddy, 2015). A unifying theme here is that improving mathematics education seems to be inherently fueled by capitalism. We should teach mathematics better so students can be better workers. We should help minority students learn mathematics so they can do better for themselves financially. Even in research regarding graduate-level education, the goal is to make sure that students are better prepared for the field of academic mathematics. I acknowledge that researchers need to justify their work to get published and to get stakeholders to pay attention, but I think that this motivation is inherently flawed because it values the output of the student over the wellbeing of the student, and it lacks a holistic understanding of what it means to flourish (Su, 2020).

I do not think mathematics education should be improved for the purpose of improving our country’s economic power. I do not think mathematics education should be improved in order to improve a student’s individual chances at achieving financial stability. Especially in the case of calls for bringing underrepresented groups into the field of mathematics, we forget that there is only so much room! There are finite high paying jobs under capitalism – no matter what is done, someone will be pushed out. This argument is more fully developed by Danny Martin’s (2019) academic work, specifically in regards to the systemic antiblackness in math education.

There is little consideration that maybe the folks being excluded from mathematics might not even want to get in anyway. Mathematics is fun and cool, sure, but if we improve mathematics education so that (for example) more women stay in the field, then what? Then you have funneled a bunch of women into a mathematics culture that is still dominated by patriarchal social norms. This is how I feel right now. We have all heard about the attempts to encourage girls to pursue math and science, but with no changes to the culture itself. With that, you are just setting up girls and women for a bad time, but now with the added pressure of being a “woman in STEM.” For me, I feel like I “owe it to feminism” to stick it out in mathematics, because women are still so underrepresented in mathematics, I am setting the cause back if I leave as well.

There is no consideration for how maybe the environment of mathematics itself is hostile to women, and the issue is not in the abilities or achievement (Herzig, 2004a, 2004b).

For me, there is a pressure to stick it out, because then I would be a badass, then I would be a woman in STEM. This reminds me of the American/Western phenomenon of the “girlboss.” The concept of a girlboss is related to white-feminist sentiments of “breaking the glass ceiling” and “nevertheless, she persisted” and “well-behaved women seldom make history.” Super trite feminist takes that make it onto wine glasses and t-shirts you can buy on Etsy. The focus of this style of feminism is entirely on individual economic equality: that is, women doing all the same stuff that men do. Rather than critiquing the system at large, women should be vying to be CEO too. (I claim that women who are billionaires are not any better than men who are billionaires.) Girlboss feminism is also highly individualistic: rather than shifting the culture at large, women are encouraged to “lean in,” to simply be more confident, and the only reason that they are oppressed is because they aren’t confident enough.

I say girlboss because I think it illustrates the issue well: women are encouraged to be girlbosses, but to be a girlboss means to stick it out under the worst conditions and adopt all the horrible practices that already exist in the male-dominated culture. In mathematics, this can mean

using more confident and assertive language in your proof-writing, being more of a hard-ass in the classes you're teaching, or not collaborating with your peers to keep a competitive edge. That's the thing: the dominant culture does not encourage humane practices such as rest, collaboration, and community care. But when we push women (and other groups) to grind in order to make it in STEM, we are asking them to mold themselves to an inhumane ideal.

What would it mean if we motivated our improvements to mathematics education with the goal of making it more humane to our students? What if we taught mathematics with the goal of sharing joy and wonder, not to improve a student's chance at earning six figures in the future?

Article continues on the next page.

Call me a slacker

Inspired by the lyrics of “Slacker II” by Canadian singer-songwriter Aidan Knight, this speaks to the feeling that I’m not doing enough when compared to my peers and the expectations of my professors and the university. In a way, I am calling myself a “slacker” before others can as a way to defend myself. Self-effacing language is a great defense mechanism, and it feels safer to say bad things about yourself before others might. Additionally, since I am already insecure about my performance in grad school, it feels better to loudly proclaim that I am slacking so that it might look like I’m self-aware of my under-performance. Nothing is more embarrassing than *actually* trying hard and falling short! The square shapes of flowers and a stately building on its side are meant to reflect the environment of graduate school or other similar institutions.

Mental Health

I would like to say that my mental health is personal and might be seen irrelevant to this project, but since autoethnography is all about vulnerability and sharing personal stories, the impact of the graduate program on my mental health is part of my work.

I was considering dropping out this past January, as usual, and I was talking it out with my close friend making a verbal list of pros and cons. One of the cons of dropping out would be losing my health insurance, which to me meant discontinuing seeing my therapist, to which my friend said, “the only reason you’re in therapy is because you’re in grad school!”

I have struggled with an anxiety disorder for years. It began to make itself apparent in high school, but really began to demand my attention in 2017. While I am more predisposed to experience anxiety, it is true that the academic environment only exacerbates the problem.

Well, it is a little more complicated than that. I do think that academic systems reward and encourage anxiety, provided your anxieties motivate you to finish your work. LeNoble and LeNoble (2021) note that stress is a badge of honor in burnout culture. I also think that people with anxious tendencies can find comfort in an academic environment for a couple of reasons. It is a controlled and fairly predictable environment; life-long students are very familiar with the norms associated with school. Additionally, school provides the promise that any causes for anxiety are short-term and fixable. For me, anxiety is an amorphous feeling that sticks itself onto external circumstances. So, even though I would be anxious no matter what is going on in my life, if I’m in school, it will feel like my anxiety is caused by the nearest assignment or exam. And while these certainly are stressors, they themselves are not the cause for my anxiety. But, I can uphold the illusion that the fix for my anxiety is just to turn in that assignment, or get past that deadline, or survive that exam next week.

In a way, constant deadlines make the anxiety feel more normal. At the same time, graduate school makes the anxiety worse. There’s a tension in how much it hurts and how hard it is to leave.

It is interesting to note that graduate school students are found to have higher rates of depression and anxiety: somewhere between 2 and 6 times the rates found in the general population (Bekkouche et al., 2022, p. 547). Researchers Bekkouche, Schmid, and Carliner (2022) examine the systemic reasons for this, arguing that:

[w]hile most work on the mental health of graduate students takes the perspective of it being an individual issue, related to individual predispositions to mental health or the individual traumas students might experience, the high numbers of students affected by mental and emotional problems suggest that the causes of mental health problems in graduate students extends beyond the individual (p. 547)

In fact, “[t]he stress of these systemic pressures may, at the least, exacerbate pre-existing vulnerabilities to mental health problems and, at the most, make themselves the causes” (Bekkouche et al., 2022, p. 547-548). In other words, it’s not just me. It is a common, well-documented reality that graduate school is generally bad for your mental health, and it seems like most of the ways universities attempt to address this issue is through better access to mental health care, rather than looking at the root of the problem!

My path to feeling better involves unclenching my vice-grip on productivity and societal expectations. It includes taking real rest days, letting myself be messy and unproductive, and getting more comfortable with just existing. These goals do not feel compatible with academia, but frankly, they aren’t compatible with American culture anyway. No matter where I look, I am being told to maximize my productivity and be my best self. (The Youtube algorithm is suggesting an aesthetic video about someone’s daily morning routine in which they wake up at 5 a.m. and drink a green

smoothie before going on a run.) I do not think my journey of anxiety management and healing will be magically easier when I leave graduate school; that said, graduate school definitely didn't help.

Article continues on the next page.

ANXIETY

ANXIETY/WORRY

ANXIETY

ANXIETY

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value

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Anxiety scams exposed

I thought this project would be incomplete without including reflections on my own mental health, which is informed by and informs my experience in graduate school. The anxiety disorder I've had since high school makes grad school harder, and the grad school exacerbates my anxiety. I also think that academic environments award anxiety to some degree, all while touting "self care" with the goal of improving productivity. Anxiety affects everything (the blue figure), and yet we are given simple solutions like eating well (the avocados), exercising, making time for yourself, etc. to combat these feelings and improve our output.

So far so good / Do it better

This two-part piece represents the feeling of doing mathematics before and after exposure to formal schooling. In *So far so good*, I chose to show a child exploring the natural world. The text reads “it’s not complicated” and “you feel fantastic about yourself.” Humans are naturally playful and exploratory, and mathematics can be a playful and exploratory subject about pattern-finding and playing with rules. Before being pushed through the school system, children have peaceful and exciting relationships with mathematics. During and after exposure to formal mathematics in school, there is nothing but pressure to do better, as shown in *Do it better*. The stone statue represents formal systems and traditional beauty. The lighthouse in the upper left corner might remind the viewer of an ivory tower. The text shows “DO IT BETTER” repeated many times, which might evoke a mantra of sorts that we find ourselves chanting as we try to survive our academic careers in math.

Quals

When I was admitted to the doctoral program in mathematics, I was completely unaware of the process of qualifying exams. I knew they were an aspect of graduate school but had often heard them referred to as a formality and something I shouldn't worry too much about. It quickly dawned on me that these exams were going to be a threat to my wellbeing and a very probable way for me to get kicked out of the PhD.

The mathematics qualifying exams (quals) are a series of two 4-hour exams on real analysis and abstract linear algebra. Qualifying exams are pretty much a norm across all STEM doctoral programs, but with varying degrees of importance or difficulty. In some departments, I understand that the qualifying exams are not too much to worry about. For some reason, the quals are really, really hard.

Pretty much as soon as other students in my cohort started attempting them, I knew that I did not want to take these tests! I saw the end of my sense of self-worth through the others: extremely low pass rates, very difficult content, and insulting scores and comments. It is truly jarring to hear someone say that they got zero points on an exam that they honestly attempted. How is that possible? I didn't want to attempt them, because (a) they seemed completely impossible to pass and (b) I knew they were going to fuck me up emotionally. I wish I had listened to that instinct.

The first time I tried out the exam, it was the time between spring and summer terms, and a couple of grad students encouraged me: they told me that they both crammed over the course of two weeks and managed to pass at least one of the exams in the winter. So, with whatever energy I had left after completing my first academic year of grad school, I holed up in my bedroom for approximately two weeks and jammed as much linear algebra knowledge into my head as possible. (Keep in mind that I had also completed the required preparatory class in linear algebra that year.) I am not really a crammer, so it was very difficult, and not at all an enriching learning experience. I came out the other end of those two weeks completely fried.

Truly, the month following that experience I was recovering emotionally. I was completely phoning it in for the online class I was teaching, and I didn't want to think a single mathematical thought ever again. But I felt like I had a chance of passing! When the scores were returned to us about a month after the exam, I had received four points on my exam, out of 40. I wasn't even close to passing! The feeling of your efforts being completely futile is crushing. But then I tried again, and it was even worse the second time!

I spent the rest of that summer either studying or feeling immensely guilty and undisciplined when I wasn't studying. I ended up in a study group that would meet every night for three weeks to work on math problems. I could have felt accomplished for all the knowledge I was gaining, but I only saw the gaps in my knowledge that continued to show. That many proof strategies and key theorems of two different areas of math in my brain felt like trying to hold Jell-O in my hand. It was wobbly, it was spilling everywhere, I was making a mess!

In the exam room I saw that those months of mental and emotional labor would turn out to be completely lost as I failed to answer the questions on the page. I actually shed tears during both exams, which is pretty wild. It definitely felt dramatic, but that's how much it hurt!

Are the quals intended to reflect that mathematics as a discipline is supposed to take over your life?

Are they designed to keep underrepresented groups out of positions of prestige and power and reward those with "innate" ability?

Were they meant to wreck my confidence and cause me to leave the graduate program?

Are we worried about handing out too many math PhDs? (to people like me?)

Are we worried that someone who is not a good test taker, or not an expert in real analysis is going to do some research? Research, a collaborative undertaking that is in no way related to taking an individual exam about old math?

I feel that there is no reason to keep PhD seekers out except in an attempt to keep mathematics exclusive and “pure,” or to preserve the mystique, status, and intellectual prestige of the discipline.

To put my experience into context, while I was trying to pass the quals, there have been multiple attempts by graduate students to organize and pressure the department into changing the structure of the quals. Some edits have been suggested, such as making it more connected to the corresponding first-year classes, or simply making it easier, or publishing an official syllabus of topics to expect on the exam; however, it seems to me that these solutions are irrelevant if the entire purpose of the exam is to be extremely difficult and weed people out. For the quals in their current state, I will borrow Gutiérrez’s (2018) language and describe them as dehumanizing.

There is an element of social stratification. Burton (2004) and Herzig (2002) emphasize the community aspect of graduate school in mathematics – what we see as success in a mathematics program is essentially full integration into a very specific community. The quals seem to fracture any community that developed prior to the exams. I feel like as soon as folks from my cohort started passing the exams, there was a social divide, and we were suddenly separated into two distinct groups. The exams are so emotional and so high-stakes – how can you trust someone who has already passed them? How can you feel any level of solidarity with someone who didn’t struggle with them, or if they did, isn’t struggling right now?

The movement to do away with quals brings out even more social disruption. It reminds me of a workplace unionizing; it also reminds me of leftists arguing on Twitter. There is no real consensus on what should replace the quals, if anything. Some mathematics graduate students still like the quals and think they should stay. Although it’s well-documented that standardized tests are biased, oppressive, bad indicators of academic quality, and favor the people you expect them to favor, it is true that some students don’t believe that. Some people think the quals should get canceled. Some think that they should simply be more humane. This is an interpersonal disruption, and the foundation of mathematical authority and standard mathematical practice is broken into pieces in this situation. A bunch of graduate students are saying “Look, the quals are bad” but then everyone’s different ideas of what to do instead illuminates everyone’s vastly different ideas of what it means to belong in mathematics, or even what mathematics is. This is not a very stable community. The quals become the reason for many students’ departures and leaving with a master’s degree is seen and felt as a consolation prize (Douglas, 1997, p. 43).

I guess that mathematics will lose me, along with many other talented mathematicians, due to these exams. While I have made my relative peace with the issue and envision a happy future far away from mathematics and academia, this is not true for everyone who is pushed out. I am tempted to say that I’m grateful for what the quals revealed to me about the program and the overall culture, but I wouldn’t wish a stressful, low-key traumatizing experience like this on myself or anyone else! Finding silver linings in adverse experiences can be used to dismiss real problems that must be addressed. I am happy I am leaving rather than spending another four years here, but maybe I could have been trusted to make that decision for myself rather than feeling forced out? Maybe we can trust graduate students with some agency to make decisions for themselves?

Postulates diagonalizability with no nontrivial Jordan cells. Thinks that if $v, Av, \dots, A^{n-1}v$ is a basis, then two of the basis vectors, $A^l v$ and $A^p v$, belong to the eigenspace E_λ of $\dim(E_\lambda) \geq 2$.

No approach with any traction and makes some incorrect statements.

Result – No Pass

NOT PASSED

Result – No Pass

Wasn't able to factor characteristic polynomial.

Shows in a cumbersome way that if $A = \lambda I$ and $\text{tr}(X) = 0$

photo: courtesy of Lubov Mazur. "After" photos: Charles Miller.

Cumbersome

Regarding some of the feedback I have received on the qualifying exams, I feel that the tone of the feedback I received is quite mean. I cut out some of the wordy feedback because I feel like it has the tone of “obviously two plus two is four, you idiot” but the actual content is very advanced. The phrasing “thinks _____” is particularly invasive, because the grader is not commenting on what I wrote, but is claiming to understand what is going on in my head, with the “obvious” truth that my thinking itself is flawed. I wanted this piece to be full of individually calm elements but the whole piece to look chaotic. It shows how I felt about the exam for months before and after taking it. I would be doing anything mundane or calm and would think about all the ways in which I was a failure. The person in the upper right corner represents myself: head in the clouds, not trying hard enough, never having a chance to pass because I can’t stop looking outside. The fisher represents the feeling of random luck involved with the quals. The cannon reflects the absolute chaos this exam caused in my life.

Fk school

This interpretation will not surprise you very much. I made this piece during one of my many phases of desperately wanting to drop out. This piece in particular shows a desire to escape (the camper) and a desire to rest (the cat). Another layer to this is the symmetry of the composition and the geometry of the blanket on the bed: both elements of mathematical beauty. This piece does not rebuke mathematics, but it rebukes academic systems.

I hardly know myself

how can that be at my age?

I'm right where I was 3 years ago

if something were to pull me

by now it would have happened

all the memoirs in the world say otherwise but I feel so old!

seeing nothing on the outline of my vision

counting up the hours I've got left on this earth

and killing them all

all of the men and jobs

I tried on once and gave away

the songs I write now sound the same

what could be possibly left to find out?

I'm back at university and I thought it would

keep me from having to choose anything for awhile

but suddenly I give all my time to things I don't care about

and getting out of bed is harder and harder

every morning

do something else

what have I been trying to find

I could just do something else

tell all my friends and family

that I'm quitting again

I lost it, I'm drifting again

I hardly know myself

I wrote this song in January 2021, during the winter term of my first year in graduate school. I was seriously considering dropping out of school during this period, partially due to a particularly difficult class I was enrolled in, partially caused by fear of the quals, and likely partially due to the detrimental mental health effects of January weather. I was realizing that I didn't have the emotional investment necessary to get through the qualifying exams, let alone complete an entire dissertation. This song comments on the feeling of having no real passion in life- while all the mathematicians around me seemed to be in math school out of love for the subject, I was here because I had nothing better to do. That felt very alienating; I felt completely isolated and out of place. The fact that I already wanted to give up on graduate school after 4 months made me feel like a commitment-phobe. I was feeling very self-conscious about all the drifting I had done since getting my bachelors. I had held a lot of jobs that I only stayed in for a few months. I thought that going to graduate school would be something I would do for a long time, to show that I was capable of commitment and stability. This song also alludes to the poor mental health I was experiencing during this time. I do not want to ignore the seasonal influences on mental health. I also seriously considered dropping out in January 2022, which is a hint to me that winter term is just hard! However, I did not want to get out of bed during this time, which screams "depression!"

To listen, use the QR code or follow this link.

<https://katyandthenullsets.bandcamp.com/track/i-hardly-know-myself-demo>

Quit being A BAG-of-BONES Weakling like I was

↑ THIS SIDE UP ↑
FRAGILE
HANDLE WITH CARE

*This
Belongs to*

MIEN

BAD?

The text on this collage comes from a MEN magazine from the 1950's. The phrase “quit being a bag-of-bones weakling like I was” came from an advertisement for a body-building program for men. This collage captures my feeling of inadequacy and desire to just get up, dust myself off, and get the degree. This collage shows that I feel like my struggling is invalid and I just need to try harder. It's related to girlbossery, and it's related to survivorship bias. I could imagine a mathematician who is further along in their career telling me that I just need to get it together and grind! The gripping hand is meant to show the white-knuckle effort involved in survival.

This belongs to men

I did not intend to make so much art about gender, but I have decided to include this piece because it is definitely about the culture of mathematics. The cigarettes and the Corvette symbolize masculinity. The two cartoon men are at ease in the masculine environment, while the woman in the top left corner is excluded. The characters at the bottom of the page are all tense observers of the scene. The squid in the top right corner could be interpreted two different ways: either it represents the beautiful mystique and discovery of mathematics, or it represents the monster below the surface that is oppression and toxicity in the field. The “FRAGILE” sign at the top also has multiple interpretations. It can either signify my feelings of fragility, or it can signify the fragile egos of male mathematicians.

In/Out

“Have you graduated yet?”

“Why are you in grad school anyway?”

“You aren’t dropping out, you’re leaving with a masters! That’s a huge accomplishment!”

My friends have the best of intentions. My friends and family are looking out for me. But it’s hard to look at the sharp divide between the reality outside the math graduate program and inside the program.

Inside:

- Leaving with a master’s degree is a consolation prize (Douglas, 1997, p. 43), and is by all accounts considered a failure.
- Spending all your free time studying is not only normal, but encouraged.
- The qualifying exams have a pass rate below 30%.
- Math is a beautiful thing, and if you don’t see the beauty, it’s because you aren’t trying hard enough.
- I am a mediocre math student.

Outside:

- A master’s degree in mathematics is a really big deal.
- Math feels like torture.
- I am working way too hard on this.
- I am a musician, artist, and friend.

I keep wondering if the reason I didn’t make it in academic mathematics is because I didn’t like mathematics enough. I lacked the discipline and motivation to keep at it in the face of adversity. I make jokes to my non-math friends along the lines of “I don’t even like math that much! I’m not even good at it!” and that’s simply not true. In fact, I do like math, but in the insular academic environment I’ve found myself in, I look and feel like a complete slacker.

I have another life outside of grad school. I am a musician, and I have been playing with my band since 2017. I have been writing music since I was 16. Was it foolish of me to think that there would be room in my life for music and academics? I feel like there is little space for mathematicians who have other passions. Everyone who knows me through the graduate program in mathematics has no idea who I am outside of math. But my community outside of the graduate program does not understand or see what’s going on inside, they just see that I’m absent, and I’m suffering needlessly. I am completely removed from my old life, and my old friends are wondering why I’m gone.

Article continues on the next page.

Just leave

I wanted this piece to feel like there's an inner world and an outer world. The inner world of math grad school is represented by the black and white five-sided piece. It is very structured and orderly, showing a row of identical people working studiously. The person with the umbrella getting blown around is how I feel: unable to survive in that environment! The crowd eating a meal outside represents the world outside of mathematics. Everyone is taking care of their physical need to eat, socialize, and rest; the world is organic, disorganized, and full of color; and the participants in the meal are blissfully unaware of what's going on inside the inner world of math grad school. The three people in the upper right corner represent my friends outside of mathematics who don't understand why I'm torturing myself and wish that I would just leave school.

if I'm sad, well I must have chosen it
 it tastes like a well drink watered down
 men and their unearned confidence
 it's hard to see past people taller than me
 tired of carving out my own space
 I'm losing it
 it's like if I died no one would notice
 if I died they wouldn't notice
 if I died at least my mom would call
 it's hard to imagine
 if I'm swimming in this **pool** by myself then why don't I just get out?
 if I'm sinking in this **pool** by myself then why don't I just get out?
 (if there was any other way, I'd be fine, I wouldn't bother you)

Pool

This song was written about two weeks into my first term of graduate school. I remember feeling shocked by how many men were in my cohort. Two isolating experiences come to mind: school was remote at the time, but we organized an in-person meetup at a park, and I was the only woman present. I also noticed that the only people unmuting themselves to speak during our very first class were men. I was feeling like I had just gotten myself into something I hadn't bargained for. I felt expendable and anonymous. I felt like the smallest fish in the biggest pond. The line "if I'm sinking in this pool by myself then why don't I just get out?" echoes the girlboss sentiments I spoke about earlier in this project. I just felt like my suffering in this program was my own doing and it was up to me to just hoist myself out of it. Either get better at math or leave now.

To listen, use the QR code or use the link below:

<https://katyandthenullsets.bandcamp.com/track/pool-demo>

Big Boy Math

Watch out for this guy! I wanted to build something around the phrase “big boy math,” which is a word I use to describe the math that “real mathematicians” do, which is more difficult to understand and more rigorous than my work. I tried to show this with images of prestige, grandeur, and glorified suffering. The rock climbing boy in the clouds can represent the heavenly knowledge that is mathematics. It also nods to rock climbing, which is another male-dominated culture where hard work and suffering are rewarded.

Big Boy Math

It feels like a cop-out to have made a project like this to earn my master's degree. It feels like the easy way out of here. It feels like people who just can't cut it in "real" math choose to do mathematics education. Mathematics education is the softer mathematics for people who just can't pass the quals. Mathematics education researchers are touchy-feely and just want to talk about their feelings in a circle. And any advancements in collegiate classroom practices are reserved for the mathematics education classes, while the real mathematicians suffer through incomprehensible lectures.

What is with the mathematician's apparent love for suffering? Why do I feel like I'm a lesser academic and mathematician for choosing to do art? In general, I am so insecure about my stance in this program because I often choose to value my own wellbeing over assignments and studying. A truly dedicated mathematician is expected to shirk all other earthly responsibilities in pursuit of pure and glorious mathematical knowledge. You are supposed to suffer for math. You are supposed to get very little sleep and be underfed. This is the coveted aesthetic of the impassioned academic. If the thing you are studying isn't interfering with your personal life, well, is it even worth doing?

I am reminded of my high school boyfriend, who was very interested in songwriting and recording. He would become so immersed in his projects that he would forget to eat, or would stay up until sunrise. He would brag about this, and I would feel like an inadequate musician, because nothing held my attention like that. I loved music, but I couldn't let it interfere with my personal needs, which I guess meant that I am not as "dedicated."

It is a masculine tradition and a privilege of the wealthy to fully immerse yourself in academic or artistic work at the expense of your earthly wellbeing. Moreover, it is a feature of the "culture of burnout" that plagues STEM (LeNoble & LeNoble, 2021). The culture of burnout encourages long hours of work without breaks, and treats stress as a badge of honor.

Big Boy Math is the mathematics that the men in my program do. It's competition, it's suffering. It's aggressive independence (Herzig, 2002, p. 202). It's an incomprehensible paper, it's teaching yourself the material with a book written by another white guy. It's the pure math research that my peers do, which comes across as more valuable than my work. And why is it more valuable? Because it's gatekept? Because it is impossible to understand? The field of mathematics has been described as at risk of becoming "an esoteric priesthood for the few" (Chan, 2006, p. 899). I think it already has.

Making this project is difficult for a couple of reasons. Not only is it an exercise in vulnerability, but I am worried that I am not doing something rigorous enough. I anticipate that some people will think that this is worthless. I am comparing myself to people studying algebraic topology, or partial differential equations, or any of those other areas of study you need a degree to understand. My friends are doing Big Boy Math, and I'm just writing a diary over here. It takes a lot of self-trust to continue.

I am also reminded of recreational rock climbing. I picked up the hobby about a year ago, and I have found indoor rock climbing at the gym to be immensely rewarding. The surrounding culture, however, reminds me of mathematics culture in some ways. The dominant ideology is pushing your body to its absolute limit and celebrating climbing routes that are nearly impossible. For something so goofy as what is basically a jungle gym for adults, rock climber bros are very serious about their suffering. I am not immune to the influence of intense climber bros and it takes a concerted effort to keep the sport as a peaceful, intuitive, non-competitive endeavor.

I do not want to push myself to the absolute limit of my abilities. I don't want to force myself to do difficult things that don't serve me. What would it mean to listen to myself?

What would it mean to listen to myself?

This is a meditation on self-compassion, intuition, and self care. I wonder about how it would be possible to move through mathematics, grad school, and life in a way that honors my own needs. As explored in *Mathematics for Human Flourishing* by Francis Su, mathematics itself can be a way to fulfill many human needs and virtues. There is no definite answer to the question posed in the text of this collage. The three dogs represent different levels of ease/anxiety. The sea glass and mint reflect the peaceful sentiment of the question posed.

TURNS OUT I WANT THIS CLASS TO END

*I want to learn math again
 Just to feel better than
 My socially adjusted friends
 And get a 95 percent
 Tiny plastic polygons
 I'm building things that aren't real
 Endless streams of hexagons
 And other fun material
 I play Jumpstart, but math's hard
 And I can't stand learning anything
 I like when people think I'm smart
 But I'm dumb, so I won't add sums up anymore
 And I barely even care that I'm forgetting all the Common Core
 I won't add sums up anymore, I won't add sums up anymore*

–“Hexagons and Other Fun Materials” by Sidney Gish

I like to say that I went to graduate school as a joke. After all, I had no idea what to do with myself, and I thought it would be kind of weird and out of character if I got a PhD in mathematics. I am lying to myself if I say that I came here completely randomly. There is a reason I chose to major in mathematics in undergrad, and there's a reason I felt like signing up for a PhD in the subject area. Mathematics could be a beautiful and compelling subject, and part of me really wants to learn it all! But I, like many other students, have found myself disappointed by the reality of studying math in the academic world.

*Turns out I want this class to end
 I don't need to learn to hate it again
 I'm falling out of my seat
 And drawing on the worksheets
 Exactly how I used to be
 And it's a blast to high-achieve,
 But only cause approval is the root of what I need,
 I guess I'll study something else
 But this time I won't hate myself*

Even though mathematics itself has the potential to be so wonderful, intriguing, and soul-healing, the context in which we learn this mathematics destroys the joy entirely. The aptly titled study “Slaughtering this beautiful math?: Graduate women choosing and leaving mathematics” by Abbe Herzig (2004b) is a fantastic example in the formal literature of this experience. The

following themes arose in Herzig's interviews with women graduate students in a particular math department: feeling invisible, needing guidance/better mentorship, wanting better teaching, and lacking moral support and encouragement (Herzig, 2004b). Herzig summarizes some of her findings in the following way:

These women had all come into the program with a passion for some aspect of mathematics, which helped motivate them to work very hard to understand mathematical concepts and ideas. [...] Unfortunately, the education they received in the department left them with a "bad taste" in their mouths, and some described having lost their love of mathematics. (p. 387)

This sucks! The coursework of graduate school all but destroys the joy of mathematical pursuit. If anything, it's impossible to enjoy oneself if the environment is so unbelievably toxic. Specifically on the level of pedagogical style, it blows my mind that courses about mathematics feels so uninspiring. Are we, as students, to be so perfectly disciplined and intrinsically motivated that we dig out the awe-inspiring beauty of mathematics buried in lectures where a professor simply reads to you from a textbook written 50 years ago? How can anyone protect their love for the subject?

It is no secret that the transmission model of education is outdated and unhelpful. In a different paper, Herzig (2004a) notes the problems with this teaching model in its effects on a student's integration into the community of practice, thereby affecting persistence: "This 'transmission' model of teaching poses teachers as knowledgeable and active (their role is to tell students all they need to know) and students as ignorant and passive (their role is to absorb the information provided to them)" (p. 179). Rather than treat students as empty vessels to be filled with knowledge, this paper advocates for students to be treated as community members or participants in mathematics. This community integration is essential for student retention, particularly for systemically excluded populations.

I know that nothing has killed my joy of mathematics faster than the impenetrable lecture classes I have taken. It's almost as if nurturing mathematical knowledge via course-taking isn't the real focus of attending graduate school and it's all about survival of the fittest! Hmm!

—

Is there hope to fix mathematics education? That's a huge question, as the shortcomings of mathematics education are seen at every age and level, not just graduate classes. Paul Lockhart (2002) has an interesting take in his particularly scathing essay *A Mathematician's Lament*:

In fact, if I had to design a mechanism for the express purpose of destroying a child's natural curiosity and love of patternmaking, I couldn't possibly do as good a job as is currently being done—I simply wouldn't have the imagination to come up with the kind of senseless, soul crushing ideas that constitute contemporary mathematics education. (p. 2)

Lockhart, among other mathematics education reform activists, are pushing for the culture-wide recognition of mathematics as an art form that is intrinsically human.

Mathematician Francis Su (2020), for instance, argues that mathematics is an intrinsic element of the human experience and an important way for humans to flourish. He states that mathematics cultivates crucial human needs, desires, and virtues: exploration, meaning, play, beauty, permanence, truth, struggle, power, justice, freedom, community, and love. Note that this list of ideas omits anything about achievement or competition. To Su, mathematics should be all about the satisfaction of human emotional needs. Indeed, there is something massively wrong with our society's views of mathematics such that people feel like they are bad at mathematics or can't do

mathematics, since “Doing math is tightly bound to being human” (Su, 2020, p. 214). Su’s book is an in-depth validation and encouragement to all to pursue mathematics for their own joy and wellbeing.

Mathematician Rochelle Gutiérrez describes the current state of mathematics education as dehumanizing and presents eight key aspects in the work required to rehumanize mathematics centered around Black, Indigenous, and Latinx students (Gutiérrez, 2018). Rather than teaching disadvantaged students to play the game, Gutiérrez advocates for changing the mathematical practice itself in order to benefit all. Using the word “dehumanizing” to describe current mathematical practice is a powerful and effective choice that really resonates with me. This eight-concept framework is a helpful guide for educators for identifying and shifting certain dehumanizing mathematical practices that may otherwise go unnoticed and unchanged. Integration of cultures and history, development of student ownership, broadening what is considered “mathematics,” and student creation are some of my favorite ideas from this paper.

To answer my earlier question, yes, there is hope for improving mathematics education. Francis Su paints a beautiful picture of what exactly mathematics can do for us intellectually, emotionally, and spiritually; and Rochelle Gutiérrez outlines exactly how math can be reconstructed in a way that is anticolonialist and benefits all students. It is inspiring work, and I wish I could be more excited about it. However, I am so burned out by my experience in graduate school that I feel like I can barely engage with these hopeful messages. Mathematics for Human Flourishing (Su, 2020) has a fun mathematical puzzle at the end of each chapter, and I noticed that I was skipping them. Even though at my core I agree with all these calls to action, I am still churning out a master’s project on a deadline in a graduate program. I am still sitting in transmission-style lectures learning old-white-guy math. I want to become a fighter for the rehumanization of mathematics because I believe in it, but I’m too exhausted and worn down for now. Get back to me in a few years.

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